

APPENDIX A SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

A. Background

Event logs serve as a mechanism for smart contracts to emit structured information during their execution, facilitating contracts to communicate with external applications and other contracts. For example, Figure 1 presents the event log for an ERC721 transfer. The address field specifies the smart contract that emitted the event log, whereas the transactionHash field identifies the transaction in which the log was recorded. The topics field stores indexable metadata associated with the event, including: 1) the Keccak-256 hash of the event signature, and 2) the encoded values of the index parameters of the event. The indexing mechanism facilitates efficient log filtering and retrieval by external applications.

```

1 {
2   "address": "0x995020804986274763df9deb0296b754f26
3     59ca1",
4   "topics": [
5     "0xddf252ad1be2c89b69c2b068fc378daa952ba7f163
6     c4a11628f55a4df523b3ef",
7     "0x00000000000000000000000000000000c17a28621227fce73b
8     51e91f188d40c18af11048",
9     "0x00000000000000000000000000000000f152b87c3503e53785
10    3e160adb7e330ea0be7c4",
11    "0x000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000014cf"
12  ],
13  "data": "0x",
14  "blockHash": "0xd8acc5ae07dcb910082d7a8a63080d048
15    385e24523425f165e45ba6ed5a41d9f",
16  "blockNumber": "0x4c54ef",
17  "blockTimestamp": "0x5a71030a",
18  "transactionHash": "0xc58c462e03038893559887ebd31
19    62be08f4accc017a6311cf4f0815e7cbbc34b",
20  "transactionIndex": "0x86",
21  "logIndex": "0x35",
22  "removed": false
23 }

```

Fig. 1: Example event log.

B. Example Contracts in Clusters

```

1 contract GC is ERC721Creator {
2   constructor() ERC721Creator("Graphicurve", "GC") {}
3 }
4 contract ERC721Creator is Proxy {
5   constructor(string memory name, string memory symbol
6     ) {
7     assert(_IMPLEMENTATION_SLOT == bytes32(uint256(
8       keccak256("eip1967.proxy.implementation")) - 1)
9     );
10    StorageSlot.getAddressSlot(_IMPLEMENTATION_SLOT).
11    value =
12    0x2d3fc875de7Fe7Da43AD0afa0E7023c9B91D06b1;
13    Address.functionDelegateCall(
14    0x2d3fc875de7Fe7Da43AD0afa0E7023c9B91D06b1,
15    abi.encodeWithSignature("initialize(string,
16    string)", name, symbol)
17    );
18  };
19 }
20 bytes32 internal constant _IMPLEMENTATION_SLOT =
21 0x360894a13ba1a3210667c828492db98dca3e2076cc3735
22 a920a3ca505d382bbc;
23 .....
24 .....

```

Fig. 2: Example *Manifold* EIP-1967 Proxy contract A (1).

```

1 contract NFT is ERC721Creator {
2   constructor() ERC721Creator("EvermoreNFTs", "NFT")
3   {}
4 }
5 contract ERC721Creator is Proxy {
6   constructor(string memory name, string memory symbol
7     ) {
8     assert(_IMPLEMENTATION_SLOT == bytes32(uint256(
9       keccak256("eip1967.proxy.implementation")) - 1)
10    );
11    StorageSlot.getAddressSlot(_IMPLEMENTATION_SLOT).
12    value =
13    0x5133522ea5A0494EcB83F26311A095DDD7a9D4b6;
14    (bool success, ) =
15    0x5133522ea5A0494EcB83F26311A095DDD7a9D4b6.
16    delegatecall(abi.encodeWithSignature("
17    initialize(string,string)", name, symbol));
18    require(success, "Initialization failed");
19  }
20 }
21 bytes32 internal constant _IMPLEMENTATION_SLOT = 0
22 x360894a13ba1a3210667c828492db98dca3e2076cc3735
23 a920a3ca505d382bbc;
24 .....
25 .....

```

Fig. 3: Example *Manifold* EIP-1967 Proxy contract B (3).

```

1 contract BAYCOthersideLand {
2   bytes32 internal constant KEY = 0
3     x360894a13ba1a3210667c828492db98dca3e2076cc
4     3735a920a3ca505d382bbc;
5 }
6 constructor(bytes memory _a, bytes memory _data)
7 payable {
8   (address _as) = abi.decode(_a, (address));
9   assert(KEY == bytes32(uint256(keccak256("
10    eip1967.proxy.implementation")) - 1));
11   require(Address.isContract(_as), "address
12   error");
13   StorageSlot.getAddressSlot(KEY).value = _as;
14   if (_data.length > 0) {
15     Address.functionDelegateCall(_as, _data);
16   }
17 }
18 .....
19 .....

```

Fig. 4: Generic EIP-1967 proxy contract (5).

```

1 contract ERC721A is Context, ERC165, IERC721,
2   IERC721Metadata {
3   function _safeMint(address to, uint256 quantity)
4     internal
5   function _mint(address to, uint256 quantity, bytes
6     memory _data, bool safe) internal
7   ....
8 }

```

Fig. 5: Example ERC721A contract (7).

```

1 library Helpers {
2   function computeCurrentDebt(uint256 amount,
3     uint256 rate, uint256 startTime) public view
4     returns (uint256)
5 }
6 function calcRefinancingAuctionRate(uint256
7   startBlock, uint256 auctionDuration, uint256
8   oldRate) public view returns (uint256)
9 }
10 function executeTakeBid(Lien calldata lien,
11   uint256 lienId, ExecutionV1 calldata execution,
12   uint256 debt, IBlurPool pool, IExchange
13   exchange, address delegate, address
14   matchingPolicy
15 ) external
16 }
17 function executeTakeAsk(LoanOffer calldata offer,
18   ExecutionV1 calldata execution, uint256
19   loanAmount, uint256 collateralTokenId, uint256
20   price, IBlurPool pool, IExchange exchange,
21   address matchingPolicy
22 ) external
23 }
24 .....
25 .....

```

Fig. 6: Example financial utility contract for NFTs (10).

C. Linguistic Topic of Semantic Clusters

TABLE I: Top ten semantic clusters with the most smart contracts in the NFT ecosystem.

Label	Source Code	Linguistic Topic from Source Code
① MANIFOLD EIP-1967 PROXY A	●	target, data, slot, value, solidity, functioncall, errormessage, returndata, dev, implementation, success, proxy, available, implementation, contracts, v3, implementation_slot, storageslot, xref, functioncallwithvalue
② UNISWAP V3 LIQUIDITY POOL	●	tick, param, liquidity, pool, position, notice, token1, token0, fee, int24, observation, amount0, amount, time, price, initialized, uint160, ticklower, tickupper, self
③ MANIFOLD EIP-1967 PROXY B	●	target, slot, value, data, solidity, returndata, errormessage, dev, success, functioncall, implementation, available, proxy, implementation, storageslot, safe, contracts, implementation_slot, v3, functioncallwithvalue
④ EIP-1167 PROXY	●	role, dev, token, set, account, value, tokenId, p0, log, p1, sol, contracts, p2, operator, import, length, abi, p3, id, zero
⑤ GENERIC EIP-1967 PROXY	●	target, value, slot, functioncall, data, returndata, errormessage, available, success, iscontract, v3, storageslot, xref, contracts, dev, functioncallwithvalue, low, level, reason
⑥ JPEG NFT	○	
⑦ ERC721A NFT	●	tokenId, owner, token, dev, contracts, ownership, quantity, addr, mintamount, ierc721, msgsender, openzeppelin, burned, _currentindex, onlyowner, operator, _ownerships, zero, error, transfer
⑧ VAULT	○	
⑨ ERC721 NFT	●	tokenId, token, owner, dev, erc721, transfer, zero, interfaceid, ierc721, operator, approved, contracts, length, id, target, file, requirements, onlyowner, supportsinterface, data
⑩ FINANCIAL UTILITY	●	reserve, user, asset, param, vars, datatypes, params, errors, self, configuration, debt, reservecache, underlying, indexed, nft, collateral, rate, id, reservedata, token

TABLE II: Top five semantic clusters of smart contracts with the highest degree of interaction occurring during transactions.

Label	Linguistic Topic from Source Code
MARKETPLACE A	order, sell, uints, addrs, buy, maker, salekind, howtocall, assetid, salekindinterface, feemethod, hash, arrayutils, taker, safemath, feemethodssideskindshowtocalls, array, add, replacementpattern, paymenttoken
MARKETPLACE B	order, conduit, consideration, item, orders, offerer, offer, mstore, items, supplied, add, indicating, array, hash, pointer, retrieve, error, execution, note, mload
PROXY REGISTRY A	implementation, proxy, addr, newowner, howtocall, user, sender, revoked, access, proxyregistry, registry, revoke, delegatecall, dest, pending, transfer, onlyowner, tells, delay, ptr
PROXY	implementation, proxy, ptr, version, representing, newowner, current, size, upgraded, newimplementation, upgradeability, tells, upgradeabilityproxy, keccak256, title, delegatecall, allows, file, position, calldatasize
PROXY REGISTRY B	implementation, proxy, addr, newowner, howtocall, user, sender, revoked, access, revoke, proxyregistry, delegatecall, transfer, dest, pending, registry, tells, ptr, allows, representing